

Quantitative Changes in Available Iron and Manganese as Influenced by Moisture Regimes of Soil

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The changes in the available forms of iron and manganese on moistening and drying the soils were studied both under normal and sterile conditions. Under normal condition moistening the soil reduced and drying increased the available and easily reducible manganese, and these were attributed to biological oxidation and chemical reduction respectively. Quantity of ferrous iron increased on wet incubation and decreased on redrying the samples under normal condition, whereas the opposite picture was noted in soils sterilized with sodium azide solution.

IRON and manganese are present in soil in more than one valence state, of which the bivalent forms are easily soluble and available to plants. In laboratory available manganese and iron of soil are commonly determined with air dried samples. Debnath¹ reported that available manganese determined in moist incubated samples shows better correlation with plant uptake of manganese than that determined in air dried samples. Increase in exchangeable manganese on air or oven drying has been reported by many²⁻⁵.

Debnath¹ observed a considerable decrease in exchangeable manganese in some soils on incubating the samples under moist condition. Such changes in manganese in soil may be due to chemical reaction or biological activities. Leeper³ and Leeper and Swaby⁶ are of opinion that microbial oxidation of manganese can take place only at pH values above 5.5, whereas the reverse process occurs at pH lower than this. So, the present investigation was undertaken to study the effect of moisture and drying of the soils of different pH values on the availability of manganese with an attempt to fix up the possible reasons for the changes.

The oxidation-reduction, and hence the availability of iron is intimately related to the quantity of various forms of manganese present in soil. So, the changes in the behaviour of iron as influenced by moisture and drying were also included in the study.

Experimental

Six soil samples (0-22 cm. depth) collected from different agroclimatic regions of West Bengal were used in the experiment. The relevant characteristics of the soils are given in Table 1.

10 g portions of ground, air dried soil were taken in glass bottles in two series. In the first series the

soil was moistened with distilled water to ensure its 50% water holding capacity. In the second series the same level of moisture was assured through one percent solution of sodium azide to check the microbial activity. Four such sets, each with two series, were incubated at a constant temperature of $30 \pm 1^\circ$. Loss of moisture during incubation, as determined by difference in weights, was made up every day with distilled water. After 15 days of incubation the first two sets were taken out and analysed for available (water soluble plus exchangeable) and easily reducible manganese and exchangeable ferrous iron as per procedure described by Jackson⁷. For estimating easily reducible manganese separate set was used.

The second set, after 15 days of moist incubation, was allowed to dry at the same temperature ($30 \pm 1^\circ$) for 7 days. The dried samples were then analysed for iron and manganese fractions. The physico-chemical properties of the soils were determined by the standard conventional methods⁷.

Results and Discussion

The available (water soluble plus exchangeable) manganese content of the soils varied from 3.4 to 5.9 ppm in air dry samples and from trace to 0.85 ppm in moist incubated samples (Table 2). The results show that incubation under moist condition decreased the available manganese content of the soils irrespective of their pH values. But incubation of the soils moistened with sodium azide solution, though, considerably increased the soil-pH, which is favourable for oxidation of manganese, did not bring out any appreciable changes in available manganese content. Almost the same behaviour was observed in case of easily reducible manganese (Table 3). This indicates that biological processes are involved in

TABLE 1. CHARACTERISTICS OF THE EXPERIMENTAL SOILS

Place of soil collection	Soil type	% Moisture (air dry)	Water holding capacity (%)	% Clay	pH (1:1)	Organic C (%)	C.E.C. me/100g
Haringhata	Alluvial	2.5	55	47.0	7.1	0.75	16.5
Chakdah	"	2.6	60	26.3	6.5	0.80	31.7
Hemaitpur	"	2.5	60	37.4	8.2	0.75	34.4
Alipurduar	Terai	3.0	50	28.0	5.4	1.06	8.9
Nakshalbari	"	3.8	58	40.0	5.0	1.07	10.8
Purulia	Red	2.0	30	42.0	6.8	0.35	13.2

TABLE 2. AVAILABLE MANGANESE AND pH OF INCUBATED SOILS

Soils	ppm Mn					pH of moist incubated soils	
	Air dry soils	Moist incubated	Moist incubated and dried	Moist with Na-azide and incubated	Moist with Na-azide, incubated and dried	Without Na-azide	With Na-azide
Haringhata	5.1	Trace	7.70	5.10	6.80	7.0	8.9
Chakdah	4.3	0.43	6.80	4.25	6.80	6.4	6.5
Hemaitpur	4.3	0.85	6.40	5.95	6.80	8.1	8.2
Alipurduar	5.1	Trace	6.80	4.25	5.10	5.4	7.0
Nakshalbari	5.9	Trace	9.40	4.68	5.95	5.1	6.9
Purulia	3.4	Trace	8.50	3.40	4.25	6.7	8.2

TABLE 3. EASILY REDUCIBLE MANGANESE CONTENT OF INCUBATED SOILS (ppm Mn)

Soils	Air dry soil	Moist incubated	Moist incubated and dried	Moist with Na-azide, and incubated	Moist with Na-azide, incubated and dried
Haringhata	29.4	21.0	29.4	29.4	29.4
Chakdah	12.6	10.5	14.7	14.7	14.7
Hemaitpur	27.3	18.9	25.2	26.3	27.3
Alipurduar	14.7	8.4	12.6	14.7	12.6
Nakshalbari	10.5	6.3	10.5	10.5	10.5
Purulia	33.6	25.2	31.5	31.5	33.6

lowering down the available manganese content of the moist soils. This can be explained in two ways; firstly, moisture provides favourable condition for the proliferation of microbial population to a great extent resulting an immobilization of available manganese; secondly, the increased microbial population increases the oxidation of manganese rendering it to unavailable form. But in case of Nakshalbari and Alipurduar soils, the alternative explanation is not in conformity with the observations of Leeper³ and Leeper and Swaby⁶, who reported that microbial oxidation of manganese can take place provided the initial pH value of the soil-agar plaque is 5.5 or more and the reverse occurs at low pH values. But they⁶ cited the work of Wolzogen-Kühr who reported that bacteria can also oxidise dissolved manganese at pH values between 4 and 5 Bromfield and Skerman⁸ reported that fungi may be responsible for the oxidation of manganese in acid soils and it has been considered that manganese oxidising organisms tend to cause a pH rise in the soil during their metabolism.

Redrying the soils again increased the available manganese both in sodium azide treated and untreated samples, the magnitude of increase being more in the latter case than in the former. These increases may be attributed mainly to chemical reduction and partly to liberation of immobilized manganese. This non-biological reduction can be represented by the equation:

This reduction of higher oxides is dependent upon (i) low pH, (ii) availability of oxidisable organic matter to act as electron donor, and (iii) oxides of manganese which differ in their redox potential⁹. Saxena and Baser⁴ reported that such changes also take place even in neutral and alkaline soils.

The results presented in Table 4 indicate that iron behaved differently from manganese. Incubation of the samples under moist condition increased

TABLE 4. EXCHANGEABLE FERROUS IRON CONTENT OF INCUBATED SOILS (ppm Fe)

Soils	Air dry soil	Moist incubated	Moist incubated and dried	Moist with Na-azide and incubated	Moist with Na-azide, incubated and dried
Haringhata	9.6	12.8	Trace	Trace	9.6
Chakdah	14.4	17.6	1.6	"	3.2
Hemaitpur	6.4	11.2	3.2	"	3.2
Alipurduar	4.8	9.6	Trace	"	6.4
Nakshalbari	19.2	25.6	1.6	"	4.7
Purulia	4.8	11.2	8.0	"	14.4

the ferrous iron, probably, due to development of anarobic condition in the microenvironment of the soils. Redrying again reduced the ferrous iron content to a very low level. The samples treated with sodium azide solution behaved in an opposite manner. Here, moist incubation decreased and redrying the samples increased the ferrous iron in all the soils. Decrease in ferrous iron due to moistening with sodium azide solution may be explained by rise in soil pH, which favours oxidation of iron; but its increase on redrying the same sample could not be explained. So, it is felt that this aspect of the behaviour of iron needs further investigation.

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